

Lagrangian and Fisher's Information Extremization (EPI) and Information

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For the case of a free particle, it is known that one may extremize a Lagrangian $L = .5mvv$, where $v = dx/dt$, to obtain: $d/dt dx/dt = 0$. In this classical case, one is interested in x and t or $x(t)$. One may think of moments i.e. powers of derivatives of $x(t)$. Given the first moment is equal to a constant, all higher moments are 0. Each moment yields a piece of information. Thus there is one piece of information, namely the constant velocity $v = dx/dt$. A second derivative $d/dt dx/dt = 0$ demonstrates there is no further information. The form $d/dt dx/dt$, however, is associated with an extremization of a function, namely $L = .5mvv$ or $\text{Integral } .5mvv dt$. Thus we argue that extremization is really linked to information found in the problem for the free particle case.

Next, we consider $.5 \text{ Integral } dt vv = .5 \text{ Integral } v dx$. This is proportional to $\text{Integral } p dx$ where p represents a physical impulse. The equation $d/dt dx/dt = 0$ shows there exists only one piece of information, regardless of the value of v . In other words, all v values satisfy this equation (where $v = \text{constant}$). In analogy, if one wishes all p values to satisfy $\text{Integral } p dx$, $p = \text{constant}$, without distinguishing p , then $x = \text{constant}/p$. This, however, is the quantum wavelength. If it is repeated, in space, one desires a periodic function in px which has a modulus of 1, i.e. an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$ namely $\exp(ipx)$. This does not follow from a Fisher's information type variation, but rather from the idea of information and two quantities of interest, namely a kind of probability $\exp(ipx)$ and x . The modulus of 1 is equivalent to the single piece of information present i.e. $v = \text{constant}$.

To see Fisher's information enter the quantum picture, one may consider a particle in a box with infinite walls. In such a case, $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are present or $\cos(px)$ if $a(p) = a(-p)$. There is one piece of information, so $d/dx \cos(px) = \text{function}(px)$. $\text{function}(px)$ is the one piece of extra information like v . Finding a second moment cannot yield any further information i.e. $d/dx d/dx \cos(px) = \text{constant} \cos(px)$. If it did not, there would be extra information in the system, but $v = \text{constant}$ is the only information. $d/dx d/dx \cos(px)$, however, follows from the extremization of Fisher's information subject to the constraint $\text{Integral } \cos(px)\cos(xp) CC = 1$. Thus we argue that in the free particle case, extremization really represents moments (shown by derivatives) and information.

We also consider the case of a potential $V(x)$ present.

Free Particle Lagrangian and Information

Nonrelativistic classical physics focuses on two variables, x and t , in particular $x(t)$. If $v = \text{constant}$, there exists one piece of information in the system. This piece of information seems to be linked to derivatives of d/dt of $x(t)$, namely $dx/dt = v$. There is no further information, so higher derivatives $d/dx dx/dt$ etc are all 0.

$$d/dt dx/dt = 0 \quad ((1))$$

shows one piece of information is present, but does not specify its value i.e. ((1)) holds for any constant velocity.

((1)), however, is in the form of an extremization of the function: $.5m v v$ i.e.

Integral dt $.5m v v \rightarrow$ extremized $\rightarrow m v \Delta v \rightarrow$ integration by parts $\rightarrow -m dv/dt \Delta x = 0$
 ((2))

One may call Integral dt $v v$ a type of Fisher's information (1) and ((2)) its extremization, but we argue that moments (i.e. powers of derivatives) and information are the underlying idea in this case.

In the relativistic free particle case,

$$L = -m_0 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((3))$$

which is not of the form of Fisher's information. There is still one piece of information, namely $dx/dt = 0$ and the basic forms are unchanged i.e.

$$p = \text{momentum} = \text{constant} = dL/dv \quad \text{and} \quad dp/dt = d/dt dL/dv = 0 \quad ((4)) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dt dx/dt = 0 \quad ((5))$$

((3)) still shows there is one piece of information and does not distinguish the value of v .

$P = mv / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ where $v = \text{constant}$ so $L = .5m v v$ does not yield $dL/dv = p$. A different L function is needed namely ((5)). One focuses on p because it represents physical impulse in a problem. Ultimately one is concerned with interactions and so p is used. Nevertheless, the ideas of information and derivatives still hold, it is just that one extremizes a non-Fisher L i.e. ((3)).

Quantum Free Particle

If one consider the nonrelativistic quantity to be extremized i.e.

$$\text{Integral dt } .5 m v v = .5 \text{ integral dx } p \quad ((6))$$

extremization of Integral dt $.5m v v$ leads to $d/dt dx/dt = 0$ which does not distinguish the value of $v = \text{constant}$. If one wishes this same property to apply to $.5 \text{ Integral dx } p$, (where $p = \text{constant}$), then:

$X \text{ range} = \text{constant}/p$ i.e. for each p one has a different characteristic length $\text{constant}/p$ where

$\text{Constant} = \hbar$ and this length is called a wavelength

Associating Integral $.5 m v v$ with $v = \text{constant}$ in order to extremize it to show $d/dt v = 0$, one may develop a relationship between p and x which contains the same information. No extremization

of $\int p dx$ has been used. A periodic function in p i.e. px which maps into $P(x)=\text{constant}$ because all x points have the same weight for constant motion is:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((7)) \text{ which is an eigenfunction of } -i\hbar d/dx \quad ((8))$$

This leads to very different physics from $dx/dt = v = \text{constant}$ where $x(t)$ means that each x point is distinguished within a constant $dx \rightarrow 0$ at each time. A wavelength associated with a given p means uncertainty in x for a fixed p .

A constant p , however, still means one piece of information. How does one create a differential equation which indicates that only one piece of information is present? For a free particle, the one piece of information has already been used, namely:

$$\text{One piece of information} = \text{All } x \text{ points have the same weight so } P(x) = \text{constant} \quad ((9))$$

This explicitly leads to the form $\exp(ipx)$ (with a modulus of 1) with no extremization needed.

Consider, however, the case of a bound particle in a box with infinite potential walls. In such a case, $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are present and:

$$\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) = \cos(px) \quad ((10))$$

The information of each x point having the same weight has been lost. It is only contained in the full form $\exp(ipx)$. one may consider moments d/dx of $\cos(px)$. Given that there is only one piece of information, we argue there may only be one derivative which yields new information i.e.

$$d/dx \cos(px) = \text{Function}(px) \quad ((11))$$

The second moment: $d/dx d/dx \cos(px)$ cannot yield new information so one may postulate:

$$d/dx d/dx \cos(px) = \text{constant} \cos(px) \quad ((12))$$

One might try to generalize this to $d/dx d/dx \cos(px) = A \cos(px) + B \text{Function}(px)$, but this breaks the periodicity in the problem.

((12)) is of the form of an extremization of:

$$\int dx d/dx \cos(px) d/dx \cos(px) \quad ((13)).$$

This may be generalized using: $P(x) = \cos(px)\cos(px)$ to:

$$\int dx P(x) \{d/dx \ln(P)\} \{d/dx \ln(P)\} \quad ((14))$$

((14)) is Fisher's information from statistics and ((12)) follows from the extremization of Fisher's information with respect to the constraint $\int dx P(x) = 1$.

Lagrangian with a Potential

The classical approach is to consider moments of $x(t)$. The first moment $dx/dt = \text{velocity}$. If velocity is constant, there is one piece of information in the system and $d/dt v = 0$. If velocity is not constant, then $d/dt v$ is not zero, so there must be more information. In general, this piece of information may depend on x and not t . In other words, one may send a particle through a region of space and notice that its velocity changes. Multiple test runs yield the same result, so there is spatial information which is not changing in time.

Newton already knew this and wrote:

$$dp/dt = \text{Force}(x) \quad ((15))$$

{Aside: Consider the case of an oscillator i.e. $\text{Force} = -kx$. Then ((15)) yields $x(t) = A \sin(\omega t)$. $dx/dt = A\omega \cos(\omega t)$. Taking higher derivatives does not yield any new functional forms. }

((15)) may be easily incorporated into the form of an extremization i.e.:

$$L = .5mv^2 - V(x) \quad ((16))$$

Quantum Case

It was shown that $\exp(ipx)$ describes a constant p without any extremization needed. What happens if there is a $V(x)$ which may create different momentum values? Each of these has an x range so for a bound situation which does not change in time, one has an overall density $W(x)W(x)$ as one had $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ for the free particle in a well with infinite potential walls. $W(x)$ is linked to $\exp(ipx)$ whose form does not depend on extremization. Thus one may postulate:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)\exp(ipx) \text{ with } a(p) \text{ weights being unknown} \quad ((17))$$

One may again use extremization, but instead of simply using $\text{Integral } P(x)dx$ as the only constraint one may introduce a second $F(x)$ one linked to impulse hits in space which change one p into another. Extremization then yields:

$$-1/2m d/dx dW/dx + dF/dx = E W(x) \quad ((18))$$

This is in the form of the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation if $dF/dx = V(x)W(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for a free particle one has one piece of information, in the form of a derivative i.e. $dx/dt = \text{constant}$. One may write a general condition which indicates that only one piece of information is present, but it loses explicit knowledge of the value i.e. $d/dt dx/dt = 0$ for all v constant values. In classical physics, one is interested in $x(t)$ and also moments or powers of derivatives of d/dt , i.e. information may limit the amount of derivatives one may take to learn something. Here the second derivative is the limit. $d/dt v = 0$ is of the form of an extremization result if one uses $L = .5mv^2$ as the function to be extremized. (Mass is added so $dL/dv = p$). Thus extremization is really a mathematical approach to introduce an extra moment i.e. show the restriction of information. $v = \text{constant}$ already shows information present, but $d/dt v = 0$ shows no further information and loses the exact value of v i.e. becomes a general statement about information.

If one considers $\int .5m v^2 dt = .5 \int p dx$ and notices that $d/dt v = 0$ displays no information about a specific v , then $\int p dx$ should also not display any information about a specific p . This, it seems, means there exists a special x range constant/ p for each p . If this is periodic in p and one wishes one piece of information, namely that $v = \text{constant}$ means all x points have the same probability weight, then $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution. This is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar/dx$ the translation generator and no extremization has been used and has a modulus of 1.

If one considers a particle trapped in a box with infinite potential walls, then $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ should be present. This is an OR situation in probability and so $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) = \cos(px)$ and one has lost the condition of the one piece of information, i.e. $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ is not constant. One piece of information, however, still seems to be present. Taking the derivative of $\cos(px)$, one obtains $-p \sin(px)$, a different function. Taking a second derivative yields $\cos(px)$ back again (multiplied by $-p^2$). Thus, one does not obtain any new information. This d/dx one piece of information condition may be manifested by extremizing $d/dx \cos(px)$ subject to $\int CC \cos(px)\cos(px) = 1$, but this is equivalent to EPI i.e. extremizing Fisher's information subject to $\int dx P(x) = 1$.

Thus we argue that information may be at the heart of the various extremization procedures used. (We have also shown in a previous note that extremization is linked to special relativity.)

References

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